

To cite this article: Dr. Saurabh Shekhar, MDS [1]; Dr Anuj Kumar, MDS [2]. *Journeying (metastatic) cancer cells seeding in the Oral Cavity.* *Kronicle of Dental Science.* Dec-Jun 2017; Vol 2 Issue 2: 1-8

Journeying (metastatic) cancer cells seeding in the Oral Cavity

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Keywords: *Metastasis, oral cancer, cancers of lung, breast, thyroid, liver, heart, lymph nodes*

ABSTRACT

Background and Settings: Metastasis is a complex organic passage of cancer cells that detach from the primary tumor and spreads to the distant tissues and/or organs, by traversing through the lymphovascular channels; at all times remaining, viable. Metastatic tumors to the oro-facial regions are rare; but when present may mimic many of the commonly occurring inflammatory and neoplastic lesions arising primarily in the oral cavity; therefore, the need for their deliberation in the differential diagnosis of oral lesions.

Aims and Objectives: The meta-analysis of the metastasis to the oral cavity is carried out to consolidate the data regarding the prevalent metastasis.

Data Sources: Original articles for inclusion was earmarked through keyword searches in PubMed indexed, Google Scholar, Medline Search, DOAJ and other search engines.

Study Eligibility Criteria: Case reports from all over the world that reported metastatic spread of cancer to the oral cavity. In total, 120 original case reports were included.

Synthesis Methods: Analysis of mean impacts and meta-regressions to examine factors that influence outcomes.

Results: Among the reported cases: breast cancer (23/120) showed maximum oral metastasis, followed by the lung (18/120). The least number of oral metastasis occurred in the case of neuroendocrine carcinoma (2/120) and the angiosarcoma of heart (1/120). All metastatic tumors presented as an asymptomatic swelling of the jaw, especially the mandible, arising within 2 months of diagnosis of the primary tumor. Many cases also reported the lip, chin

numbness syndrome; a diagnostic sign for oral metastasis.

Limitations: Incomplete history of the reported cases was a major drawback of this study.

Conclusion: The meta-analysis provides robust evidence that would educate the dental physicians, with respect to the varied oral manifestations of the metastatic lesions to the oral cavity.

INTRODUCTION

The metastasis to the oral cavity is uncommon, and only about 1 % of oral malignancies have been categorised as metastatic lesions. However, the frequency of metastatic tumors to the jaws is perhaps more than what has been reported; micro-metastatic foci in the jaws have been identified in 16 % of the autopsied carcinoma cases in spite of the absence of radiologic findings. Because of its rarity and the significance of early recognition, the diagnosis is challenging. Metastatic lesions do not have a specific site of occurrence although the molar-ramus area has been frequently affected. In the case of the oral soft tissues, the gingiva is the favoured site probably due to the theory of inflammation attracting metastatic deposits. The most common primary tumors presenting oral metastases in men were the lung, kidney, liver, and prostate, whereas in the women the breast, female genital organs, kidney, and colo-rectum cancers metastasised to the oral cavity. Most patients with jaw metastasis complained of swelling, pain, and paraesthesia, mostly, after a minimum period of 40 months from the discovery of the primary tumor.

The process of metastasis was first described by Paget in his 'seed and soil' hypothesis. The inflammatory microenvironment at the distant site has been considered a favourable pre-metastatic position for tumor cells to recuperate and proliferate. Tumor-associated macrophages, cancer-associated fibroblasts and infiltrating lymphocytes release various

inflammatory mediators such as TGF- β , TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-10 that promote tumor cell proliferation and dissemination.

Bone metastases involve a multidimensional boundary between metastatic tumour cells (MTC) and osteo-microenvironment which plays a crucial role in lodging and growth of tumor cells and increases manifestation of growth factors, that is required for tumor survival.

Almost half of the patients with bone metastases develop multiple complications called the skeletal-related events (SRE). They include the pathological fractures, bone pain, hypercalcemia, and spinal cord compressions. [84]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

By scanning through data available online, of the articles on Oral Metastasis, published between 2005-2017, from PubMed indexed, Google Scholar, Medline, DOAJ and other indexed journals were included in the study.

RESULTS

Of the 120 cases, the patients between 50-60 years (26/120) (Table 1) predominantly showed oral metastasis, whereas less cases of oral metastasis were observed between 80-100 years (2/120); there were a total of 65/120 males and 55/120 females among them. (Table 2)

Table 1 and Graph 1: Distribution of patients in the various age groups ranging from 20-100 years with oral metastasis

Age	20-30	31-40	41-50	51-60	61-70	71-80	81-90	91-100
	3	7	8	26	12	13	2	2

Table 2, Graph 2: Distribution of cases based on sex predilection

Sex/ Total	Males	Females
	65	55

Table 3: Distribution of the oral metastatic lesions from the common primary tumours based on age and sex

Breast	Total cases		Age	Sex	Male	Female
	23		30-40=5		0	23
			40-50=3			
			50-60=6			
			60-70=4			
			70-80=1			
			80-90=2			
Hepatocellu	7		50-60=2		6	1
			60-70=0			
			70-80=4			
			80-90=1			
Thyroid	13					
			30-40=2		3	10
			40-50=2			
			50-60=4			
			60-70=4			
			70-80=2			
Non-Hodgkin's lym		1	68		1	
Neuroendocrine Carcinom		2	38			1
Angiosarcoma of Heart		1	39			1
Genital	7		40-50=1		3	4
Organs			50-60=3			
			60-70=1			
			70-80=2			
Colorectal Cancer			40-50=1			
	14		50-60=4		14	2
			60-70=2			
			70-80=6			
			80-90=1			
Pancreas	2		70-80=2		2	0
Lung	18		30-40=2		12	6
			40-50=2			
			50-60=5			
			60-70=4			
			70-80=2			
			80-90=3			
Prostrate	9		60-70=4		9	0
			70-80=4			
			80-90=1			
Renal Cell	17		20-30=1		14	3
			30-40=1			
			40-50=0			
			50-60=6			
			60-70=7			
			70-80=2			

DISCUSSION

Wells A et al. (2013), in their study, found the bone to be the likely site of metastasis of solid neoplasms, mainly the breast, prostate, thyroid, kidney, and lungs. A similar observation was made in our study, where breast (12/120) and thyroid (5/120) showed maximum jaw bone metastasis. However, in most cases, bone-only metastasis was infrequent. Hirshberg A, et al (2008) and D'Silva NJ, et al. (2006) found that among the jaw bones, the mandible was more frequently involved than the maxilla, with the molar area being the most frequent site (> 50 %) followed by the premolar (38 %) and the angle-ramus (29 %) site, comparable to our study where lung (7/120) and thyroid (5/120) cases showed maximum mandibular involvement especially in the angle- molar-ramus area.

Data reported from National Center for Health Statistics of cases in the USA, showed that the prostatic malignancy, is the most common cancers affecting males, followed closely by the lung, colo-rectum, and urinary bladder (28, 14, 9, and 6 % respectively). In women, the breast was leading cancer followed by the lung and colo-rectum (29 and 14% respectively). [84]The liver was found to be the standard primary site for man as was reported by a study from Korea, while thyroid carcinoma was the predominant site for women; in Japanese women, the uterus was the most common primary site from where tumor spread to the oral cavity. [85]

In order for the metastatic cells to flourish and propagate the malignant tumor cells not only act on bone cells; osteoblasts and osteoclasts, but also exert control over the functions of other bone marrow residing cells, namely, the myeloid cells, immune cells, platelets, and nerve cells and the homeostasis between bone formation and destruction decides the state of the metastatic lesion whether osteolytic or osteoblastic; in most cases, bone metastases has both the osteolytic and osteoblastic components. Prostate cancer shows more of osteoblastic bone changes, which is mostly immature woven and of poor quality. Cells playing a role in the progression and development of bone metastasis could serve as biomarkers in the early detection and monitoring of the metastatic disease. [84]

Allon I, et al (2014) and Seoane J, et al. (2009), in their meta-analysis and study respectively, found that among the oral tissue sites the gingiva was the most favoured location; and Allon I and D'Silva NJ, et al. (2006) found the attached gingiva (60 %) most affected followed by the tongue (18 %). In our study the breast (8/120) and lung (8/120) showed maximum soft tissue spread especially to the gingiva.

A literature analysis has found a synergetic association between gingival metastasis and the presence of teeth, signifying the possible role of inflammation in the spreading of metastatic deposits to the gingiva. The microenvironment present in the chronically inflamed gingiva may provide a favourable site for metastatic cells to breed and multiply. IL-1 and TNF- α , the soluble cytokines, present in the chronically inflamed gingiva enable the metastatic progression by stimulating angiogenesis and hastening the generation of extracellular matrix necessary for tumor stroma and also may appeal to the tumour-associated macrophages. [84]

Among the clinical presentations of the lesion in our study, pain in the jaws was the predominant symptom, mandible

>than maxilla; posterior > anterior. In case of the maxilla, the anterior part of the jaw was most affected, including the hard palate and the soft palate. Limited mouth opening was reported in 1-2 cases due to the involvement of the retromolar area. The gingiva and buccal vestibule were the commonest soft tissue sites in case of all malignancies, followed by the tongue: our meta-analytic study did not find any tongue involvement, similar to the reporting of Hirshberg A et al. (2014). There were no associated lymph node swellings in these cases as was observed in the study conducted by us. Lymph node metastasis occurs in primary oral malignancies. The duration of the lesion in most cases is 2 months, several weeks, etc. but is it observed overnight like primary lesions of the oral cavity. Lip and chin numbness have been reported in a large number of cases thereby hinting at a sign of oral metastasis. It was found to be a predominant feature in the case of the breast metastasis (5/120). Mucosa is intact over the swelling in most cases. Bleeding from the lesion has been reported in few cases. Radiographic methods have shown the bony involvement to be radiolucent rather than opaque, simulating osteomyelitis.

The swelling is mostly described as a firm, red nodule or merely an expansile growth when the jaw bone is affected, similarly to our study where the oral lesion is described simply; as a diffuse, expansile swelling. [84]

Metastatic lesions rising from extraction sockets as a soft tissue mass extrusion has been described. [84]Only a single case manifested as a lesion arising from an extraction socket.

The most common primary sites were the lung and liver, as opposed to our study where the breast and lung were the most popular primary sites; the jaws, especially the mandibular jaw and gingiva was the most common metastatic site, followed by the tonsil/pillar, mandible, and tongue. [84] Very few cases showed metastasis to the tonsil/pillar and tongue in our study.

Gingiva was the most favoured soft tissue site of metastasis followed by the tonsil/pillar (6 cases), mandible (4 cases), tongue (2 cases), tongue base (2 cases), hard palate. [84]

The "numb chin syndrome" should raise the suspicion of a metastatic disease in the mandible, though this may also suggest a benign odontogenic tumor, trauma, odontogenic infection, etc. In many cases as in our study, bony swelling with tenderness over the affected area is the manifestation. Radiographic "moth-eaten" appearance simulating osteomyelitis must raise suspicion of a metastatic lesion. Pathologic fractures may be another common manifestation. The resemblance to a hyperplastic or reactive lesion, such as the peripheral giant cell granuloma, pyogenic granuloma or fibrous epulis may also be seen.

The mean time for the occurrence of the oral metastases has been reported to be 40 months, with over 10 years reported in some cases; whereas our study cases have reported the occurrence of metastasis within only 2 months of occurrence of the primary lesion. [84]

In many selected case reports, the exact site of oral involvement has not been stated very clearly. (6/120)

Table 4: Representation of the specific site of involvement of metastatic oral lesions

	Max			Mand			Tongue	Gingiva		Floor of mouth		Undisclosed Site	Up Parosteal Site	Trigemina I Neuralgia	Subman gland
	Ant	Post	Palate	Ant	Post	Retromolar		Mandibular ant	Mandibular post	Max ging					
Lung	2 (11 region)			1			1	4	4			6			
Breast		3		4	7	1	1	4	3	1				5	
Colorectal Cancer			1		4	1	2	1	1	1	1			1	1
Hepato cellular					4	1				1					
Genital Organ			1		1				2	1					
Pancreatic cancer							1								
Hodgkin's									1						
Neuroendo		1								1					
Leliomyo sarcoma						1									
Thyroid		1				5				5					1
Prostrate				1	1	4			3	1					

CONCLUSION

Because of its rarity, (1%) of all malignant mouth neoplasms, the diagnosis of metastatic lesions to the oral cavity is very often missed. In many cases, it may sometimes mimic a benign process. Metastasis occurs mainly through the hematogenous route of spread of the primary malignant tumor, for which, there must be a hematopoietically active bone marrow that is normally well connected with sinusoidal vascular spaces at the site of seeding of the malignant cells. Some of such sites include the focal osteoporotic bone marrow defects, the posterior mandible and the edentulous mandible; that may attract metastatic tumor cells.

The diagnosis of a metastatic lesion to the oral cavity is challenging, both to the clinician and to the pathologist. The prognosis of metastatic lesions to the oral cavity is normally very poor and combination chemotherapy to ease the symptoms is the only favoured therapeutic modality. Hence, it is necessary to assess carefully the clinical and histopathological features that would lead to the definitive diagnosis of the metastatic lesion and its origin.

FOOTNOTES

Fund source: No funds have been received towards this article

Conflicting Interest: Authors have no conflict of interest regarding this article

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